

Spectrophotometric determination of vanadium(v) as its 6-chloro-3-hydroxy-2-[2'-(5'-methylfuryl)]-4H-chromen-4-one complex

N. Agnihotri, R. Dass and J. R. Mehta*

Department of Chemistry, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra-136 119, Haryana, India

Manuscript received 26 April 1999, revised 27 September 1999, accepted 12 February 2000

A simple and sensitive spectrophotometric method for the determination of vanadium(v) has been developed using 6-chloro-3-hydroxy-2-[2'-(5'-methylfuryl)]-4H-chromen-4-one as a complexing ligand. The dark yellow (1 : 1) coloured species extracted into chloroform from 0.3 M CH₃COOH medium shows λ_{max} at 432 nm. The method is free from the interference of a large number of elements especially the platinum metals. It obeys Beer's law in the range of 0.2–1.4 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ V^V with molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of $3.98 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 0.0012 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, respectively. Analysis of various synthetic and technical samples has been carried out with satisfactory and reproducible results.

Various chromone derivatives^{1,2} used for the determination of vanadium spectrophotometrically do not provide rapid, sensitive and selective methods required for routine analysis of the metal ion. In course of investigations, it has been observed that 6-chloro-3-hydroxy-2-[2'-(5'-methylfuryl)]-4H-chromen-4-one (CHMFC), though possessing similar chelating ability with vanadium(v) yet enhances sensitivity, selectivity and speed of determination significantly as compared to the above reagents when the complex is extracted into chloroform.

Results and Discussion

In weakly acetic acid media, CHMFC formed a yellow complex with vanadium(v) which absorbed maximally in the range 426–437 nm. The reagent blank also showed absorbance to a small extent at this wavelength.

The extraction of the complex was found to be maximum in case of chloroform, whereas other organic solvents gave relatively low extraction in the decreasing order as : 1,2-dichloroethane > benzene > toluene > carbon tetrachloride > ethyl acetate > isoamyl alcohol > isobutyl methyl ketone > isoamyl acetate > cyclohexane > 1-butanol. A single extraction with equal volume (10 ml) of chloroform gave quantitative extraction as indicated by the complete absence of vanadium in the raffinate tested by highly sensitive 5,7-dichlororoxine-rhodamine 6G method³. The absorbance was stable for more than 2 h.

The optimum values of other parameters found for achieving maximum and constant absorbance were : 0.18–0.44 M acetic acid medium, 0.75–1.05 ml of 0.3% (w/v) CHMFC solution (in ethanol) for $\leq 17 \mu\text{g V}^{\text{V}}$ present per 10

ml aqueous solution maintained at 33–35° and equilibrating once with an equal volume of chloroform for 15–180 s. Beer's law was valid in the concentration range 0–1.7 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of vanadium. However, the optimum range of determination as evaluated from Ringbom plot was found to be 0.27–1.44 ppm. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were $3.98 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 0.0012 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, respectively. The reproducibility of the method was tested by performing ten sets of experiments keeping same amount (1 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) of metal ion each time, the standard deviation found was ± 0.0015 absorbance unit. The stoichiometry of the extracted species was confirmed to be 1 : 1 by Job's method of continuous variations as modified by Vosburgh and Cooper and mole-ratio methods.

Effect of diverse ions : Under the optimum conditions of the proposed method containing 10 $\mu\text{g V}^{\text{V}}$, the ions/complexing agents added as their sodium or potassium salts in 10 ml aqueous phase (mg amounts in parentheses) such as thiourea (100), chloride, sulfate, sulfite (90 each); bromide, iodide, thiocyanate (80 each); nitrate (70); phosphate (50); fluoride (10); acetate, tartrate (7 each) and citrate (1) did not influence the absorbance of the complex. The tolerance limit was set as the amount of foreign ion which caused an error of ± 0.01 in the absorbance measurement. This approximately corresponds to $\pm 1\%$ error in the recovery of vanadium. However, oxalate, EDTA, H₂O₂ and ascorbic acid hindered the formation of the coloured complex. Among the cations, Mg^{II}, Cd^{II} (10 each); Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Pd^{II}, Sr^{II}, Al^{III}, Co^{II} (9 each); Hg^{II}, Ba^{II}, Mn^{II}, Th^{IV} (8 each); Ca^{II}, Be^{II} (5 each); Cu^{II} (4); U^{VI} (3); Ce^{IV} (1); As^V, Bi^{III}, Se^{IV}, Ti^{IV} (0.5 each); Ag^I (0.2); Nb^V, Sb^{III} (0.1 each); Ir^{III},

Table 1. Comparison of the present method with other methods

Sl no	Aqueous conditions	Solvent, $\lambda_{\max}$, nm	Sandell's sensitivity, $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ Molar absorptivity, $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$	Interfering metal ions
1	V ^V , pH 3.0–4.5 moist in DMF ^a	Pentanol, 530	–	Fe ^{III} , W ^{VI}
2	V ^V , pH 2.8–4.8, 3-hydroxyflavone ^b	Chloroform, 480	0.009, 5.5×10^3	Fe ^{III} , W ^{VI}
3	V ^V , HClO ₄ , persulfate acetone, ammonium acetate, pH 3–3.5, waiting time 5 min, 1-(2-pyridylazo)-2-naphthol (PAN) ^c	Chloroform, 615	0.003, 1.69×10^4	Cr ^{VI} , Fe ^{III} , Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , U ^{VI} , Bi ^{III}
4	V ^V , pH 3.5–4.5 ^e	0.1% Oxine in chloroform, 550	0.016, 3.18×10^3	Ti ^{IV} , Fe ^{III} , Cu ^{II} , Mo ^{VI} , W ^{VI} , U ^{VI} , Bi ^{III}
5	V ^V , 0.05 M H ₂ SO ₄ , ferion ^d	1-Butanol, 430	0.011, 4.58×10^3	Mo ^{VI} , W ^{VI} , Fe ^{III}
6	V ^V , pH 6–8, dithionite, 5,7-dibromo-8-hydroxyquinoline ^e	Chloroform, 420	0.006, 7.27×10^3	Mo ^{VI}
7	Present method	Chloroform, 432	0.0012, 3.98×10^4	Mo ^{VI} (37 metals ions do not interfere)

^aRef 1, ^bRef 2, ^cRef 7, ^dRef 8, ^eRef 9

Pt^{IV}, Cr^{VI} (0.09 each); Cr^{III}, W^{VI}, Re^{VII} (0.08 each); Ta^V (0.07); Ru^{III}, Au^{III} (0.05 each); Os^{VIII} and Pd^{II} (0.02 each) caused less than 1% error. Sn^{II}, Fe^{III} and Zr^{IV} did not interfere in the presence of respective masking agents as mentioned under the procedure. However, Mo^{VI} even in traces interfered seriously by enhancing the absorbance of the complex to about four-fold.

Applications · The proposed method for the determination of vanadium(v) was rapid (took <5 min for single operation), sensitive (ϵ in the order of 10^4) and free from the interference of a large number of metal ions (viz. Ti, Fe, Cr, Mn, Co, Ni, Cu, W, U, Bi, Al and platinum metals) which interfered in most of the methods employed for its determination^{1,2,6,7}. The applicability of the method was tested by satisfactory analysis of a large variety of samples including water samples, high speed steel and reverberatory flue dust. The results obtained were highly reproducible. The method compared favourably with the existing methods of vanadium determination (Table 1).

Experimental

A Shimadzu 140-02 spectrophotometer with 10 mm matched quartz cells was used. Solutions of V^V, other ions and acetic acid were prepared as reported earlier¹. 6-Chloro-3-hydroxy-2-[2'-(5'-methylfuryl)]-4H-chromen-4-one (CHMFC), m.p. 204–206°, was synthesized by the literature method⁵, and dissolved in ethanol to give 0.3% (w/v) solution. Chloroform (Ranbaxy) was distilled and b.p. 60–61° fraction was used for extraction.

Synthetic samples were prepared by mixing solutions of vanadium(v) and other metal ions in suitable proportions. High speed steel super rapid extra 500 and reverberatory flue dust samples were brought into solution as reported⁶ and vanadium determined in the aliquots by the proposed method after adding sodium fluoride (5 mg) in each case. Water samples (10 ml each from tap and well) were mixed with a known amount of vanadium (0.01 mg), 6% H₂O₂ (1 ml) and aqueous ammonia (2 ml). The solution was boiled and evaporated to dryness, the residue dissolved in 0.3 M CH₃COOH and vanadium determined by the proposed method.

Procedure : To a sample solution containing $\leq 17 \mu\text{g}$ of V and other metal ions, were added 2 M CH₃COOH (1.5 ml), 0.3% (w/v) CHMFC (1 ml) and enough deionized water to raise the aqueous volume to 10 ml. The temperature was maintained at 33–35° and the aqueous phase was then equilibrated with chloroform (10 ml) once for 30 s. The dark yellow organic phase after separation, was poured over anhydrous sodium sulfate (2 g) to remove any retained water. The absorbance of the extract was measured at 432 nm against a reagent blank. The amount of vanadium was determined from the calibration curve obtained as per the proposed procedure.

For each of 0.05 mg Sn^{II} and 0.01 mg Fe^{III}, 5 and 10 mg sodium fluoride, respectively, were added to mask these metal ions before the addition of CHMFC in 10 ml aqueous volume. Upto 0.02 mg of Zr^{IV} did not interfere

when excess (1.5–2.0 ml) of CHMFC was added before the extraction of the complex.

Acknowledgement

Sincere thanks are due to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of a Senior Research Fellowship to one of the authors (N.A.).

References

1. R. S. Chauhan and L. R. Kakkar, *Ann. Chim. (Rome)*, 1991, **81**, 179 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1992, **116**, 50458); H. Kohara, N. Ishibashi, Y. Hanamura and K. Ueno, *Bunseki Kagaku*, 1966, **15**, 938; S. Ya Shnaiderman and G. N. Prokof'eva, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1967, **25**, 2368; N. Ghai, R. Dass and J. R. Mehta, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1997, **36**, 457; N. Agnihotri, R. Dass and J. R. Mehta, *Chem. Anal. (Warsaw)*, 1997, **42**, 397.
2. H. Kohara, N. Ishibashi and Y. Ito, *Bunseki Kagaku*, 1967, **16**, 315.
3. R. L. Varma, M. L. P. Reddy, T. P. Rao, C. S. P. Iyer and A. D. Damodaran, *Chem. Anal.*, 1997, **42**, 71.
4. N. Agnihotri, R. Dass and J. R. Mehta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1998, **75**, 514.
5. J. Algar and J. P. Flynn, *Proc. R. Ir. Acad., Ser. B*, 1934, **42**, 1; T. Oyamada, *J. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1934, **55**, 1256.
6. N. Agnihotri, R. Dass and J. R. Mehta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1998, **75**, 486.
7. Z. Marczenko, "Spectrophotometric Determination of Elements". Wiley, New York, 1976.
8. N. Kurmaiah, D. Satyanarayana and V. P. R. Rao, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1966, **35**, 484.
9. S. P. Arya and M. Mahajan, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1997, **74**, 66.